

21GRD10 – quantiAGREMI

D3: Evaluation report based on the results of the testing, calibration and validation measurements for new and existing sensors for a better estimation of livestock emissions

Organisation name of the lead participant for the deliverable:

PTB

Due date of the deliverable: Dec 2024

Actual submission date of the deliverable: Dec 2025

Confidentiality Status: PU - Public, fully open (remember to deposit public deliverables in a trusted repository)

Deliverable Cover Sheet

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The project has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

European Partnership Co-funded by the European Union

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Summary	5
2	Experimental design.....	5
2.1	The tested sensors and instruments.....	5
2.2	Reference materials	8
2.3	Testing laboratories.....	8
3	Results.....	11
3.1	Laboratory tests of Senseair and Vaisala sensors at WR.....	11
3.2	Laboratory tests of the AMON ammonia sensor performed at IMT Nord-Europe.....	15
3.3	Testing Gasera's photoacoustic spectrometer prototype at PTB	18
3.4	Laboratory and field tests of high-end NH ₃ instruments performed at TNO	20
4	Conclusions	26
5	References	26

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Glossary

The following abbreviations are used in the text:

CMI - Cesky Metrologicky Institut, national metrology institute of the Czech Republic

IMT Nord-Europe - Institut Mines-Telecom

LNE - Laboratoire National de métrologie et d'Essais, national metrology institute of France

PTB - Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt, national metrology institute of Germany

TNO - Nederlandse Organisatie voor Toegepast Natuurwetenschappelijk Onderzoek

TÜBİTAK - Türkiye Bilimsel ve Teknolojik Arastırma Kurumu, national metrology institute of Turkey

UKCEH - UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology

VSL - VSL B.V., national metrology institute of the Netherlands

vTI -. Johann Heinrich von Thuenen-Institute

WR - Wageningen Livestock Research

Units: in metrology the units $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ and nmol/mol are used for expressing amount of fraction of substances in gases. These are equivalent to the units ppm (ppmv) and ppb (ppbv), respectively, which are commonly used in environmental science. For simplicity, we use the units ppm and ppb in this document.

1 Summary

This report summarizes the results of laboratory testing of sensors and instruments, which were newly developed within the quantiAGREMI project¹, as well as other state-of-the-art sensors and instruments. Zero reading, linearity, repeatability, dependence on ambient temperature as well as cross-sensitivity to other analytes (most importantly to humidity) have been tested under laboratory conditions in various laboratories. Comparison to reference instruments and reference gas mixtures characterized in the project enabled determining accuracy and uncertainty of the sensors.

2 Experimental design

2.1 The tested sensors and instruments

2.1.1. Sensors

A literature survey on low-cost sensors has been conducted and allowed to identify the technical principles set up by sensors. The main technologies currently used for sensitive elements of sensors depend on the nature of the measured pollutant and are described below for each analyte:

- *Non-Dispersive Infrared (NDIR) spectroscopy* (CH₄, CO₂ and N₂O): This technique involves measuring the absorption of infrared light at specific wavelengths corresponding to the compounds absorption bands to determine the concentration of a given pollutant. NDIR sensors are known for their stability over time and their accuracy. They also have good sensitivity (from a few hundred to a few thousand ppm), their response time is relatively short (from 20 to 120 s) and their drift is limited over time. However, they are sensitive to ambient conditions (temperature, relative humidity and pressure).

A commercial NDIR CO₂ sensor from *Vaisala*² has been tested and used in field measurements in the project.

The *Sensair*³ K96 sensor is a prototype of compact high-resolution multi-channel NDIR sensor that is currently under development. The K96 introduces the multi-gas capability as key feature and can be configured to measure simultaneously either CH₄ or N₂O in combination with H₂O and CO₂. One

unit of each model, integrated in a thermally stabilized enclosure with active sampling (0.7-1 L/min) and data logging capability were deployed in field measurement campaigns of the quantiAGREMI projects and were tested in the laboratory at WR.

- *Electrochemical sensors* (NH₃) are based on a chemical reaction to detect a target molecule by transforming this information into an electrical signal. A contact between two conductive phases of different natures will allow a transformation or an exchange of compounds at an electrochemical interface, for example between two ionic conductors (ionic junction) or between an ionic conductor and an electronic conductor (electrode). Their advantages are their low power consumption, which make them suitable for mobile or wireless applications; their linear and stable behaviour, which means they can quantify gas concentration without being influenced by changes in pressure or flow rate; and their high sensitivity and some selectivity. Apart from its high price, this type of sensor has the

¹ <https://www.uknml.com/our-programmes/metpart-quantiagremit/>

² <https://www.vaisala.com/en/products/instruments-sensors-and-other-measurement-devices/instruments-industrial-measurements/gmp252>

³ <https://senseair.com/>

disadvantage of requiring frequent maintenance to guarantee its performance over time. In addition, it can be affected by relative humidity, temperature variations or the presence of other gases. This type of sensor also has a short lifespan due to abrasion of the electrodes and membranes and should be changed every 2 or 3 years. The *Dräger Polytron 8100* NH_3 sensor⁴ was used in field measurements in the quantiAGREMI project and tested in the laboratory at WUR.

- *Chemiresistive sensors* (NH_3): A wide range of materials have been investigated for sensing ammonia (NH_3) including metal oxides, graphene, carbon nanotubes, conductive polymers (CPs), and hybrid composites. Among these, CPs represent a promising alternative owing to their low cost, easy processing, tunable properties, and, most importantly, their ability to operate at room temperature. Polyaniline (PANI) offers additional advantages such as straightforward electrical doping and good environmental stability. In the context of NH_3 sensing, PANI demonstrates superior sensitivity compared with other polymers, primarily due to its strong acid–base interactions with ammonia in the doped state. As a result, significant research efforts have focused on employing PANI as the primary active layer in chemiresistive devices for ammonia detection. An example for this is *the AMON sensor*⁵ developed at *IMT-Nord-Europe*. The sensitive surface used for AMON sensors is prepared by drop-casting a solution composed of polyaniline (PANI) doped with camphor sulfonic acid (CSA) and dissolved in dichloroacetic acid (DCAA), with addition of Polyurethane (PU), which limits humidity interference. The reaction between the sensitive surface and NH_3 induces a variation of the material's conductivity and thus leads to variations of the resistance of the sensor. These variations of the sensitive surface's resistance are then transformed into voltage variations that can be transferred and recorded by a computer. In the field, Amon sensors are connected to a device (OEEIL) that stores and send remotely data using the 4G network.
- *Tunable diode laser absorption spectroscopy (TDLAS)* deploys diode lasers with wavelengths depending on the species of interest. Its wavelength is tuned to target a specific absorption line of the selected compound, and the measured intensity after passing through the gas containing this compound can be related to concentration by the Lambert-Beer law. It offers low detection limits (nmol/mol range) and high selectivity but needs temperature compensation. Although miniaturized TDLAS sensors are available at a price much lower than other, more sophisticated laser spectrometers, they are still expensive compared to other sensor technologies. In this work we report laboratory testing results of a CH_4 sensor from *Axetris*⁶, which was also used in field measurements in the quantiAGREMI project.

2.1.2. Instruments

In addition to the sensor tests, TNO tested 2 types of commercially available NH_3 analyzers for their application in the field, which offer much higher sensitivity than low-cost sensors: the HT8700E open-path instrument from Healthy Photon and the TILDAS-QCL closed-path instrument from Aerodyne.

- The *Healthy Photon HT8700E*⁷ is an open-path ammonia (NH_3) analyzer that utilizes advanced Quantum Cascade Laser Absorption Spectroscopy (QCLAS) for ultra-sensitive and fast-response measurements. It features a pump-free design with multiple laser reflections between highly reflective mirrors, enabling accurate detection of NH_3 concentrations over a long (folded) optical path. Designed for field deployment, it offers strong environmental adaptability, low power consumption, and optional upgrades like auto-cleaning and mirror heating for reliable performance in diverse conditions. The HT8700E is particularly suited for eddy covariance flux studies, providing high-precision data on ammonia exchange in ecosystems, however, it requires regular calibration.

⁴ https://www.draeger.com/en_uk/Products/Draeger-Polytron-8100

⁵ <https://anemon-sensors.com/en/nos-produits/>

⁶ <https://www.axetris.com/en/product/LGD-Compact-A-CH4/>

⁷ <https://en.healthyphoton.com/shengtai/products/29.html>

- The Aerodyne TILDAS NH₃ analyzer⁸ is a compact instrument that uses Quantum Cascade Tunable Infrared Laser Direct Absorption Spectroscopy (QC-TILDAS) for highly sensitive and specific ammonia measurements. The system is designed for unattended operation and eddy covariance flux studies. It achieves sub-50 ppt precision with fast time response (up to 10 Hz). The system includes an inertial inlet for filter-less particle separation and offers optional active passivation to improve response time for sticky molecules like NH₃.

Additionally, PTB and Gasera have investigated the potential for simultaneously detecting NH₃, CH₄, H₂O and N₂O with one quantum cascade laser in a photoacoustic analyzer. Gasera developed a prototype of such a spectrometer, which offers high enough sensitivity to detect ambient levels of all four analytes.

Table 1 summarizes the main characteristics of sensors and analyzers, which were tested within the project.

Table 1: The tested sensors and analyzers

Manufacturer	Sensor or Instrument	Tested at	Sensor or instrument name and/or type	Measured analytes and tested concentration range
IMTelecom	Sensor	IMT	AMON (Ammonia MONitoring Sensor) coupled with OEEIL (Individual Exposure Assessment Tool) system	NH ₃ : 0-200 ppb
Senseair	Sensor	WR	K96 1138E multi-channel NDIR sensor prototype	CH ₄ : 0-3200 ppm H ₂ O: 0-32000 ppm CO ₂ : 0-32000 ppm
Senseair	Sensor	WR	K96 115B5 multi-channel NDIR sensor prototype	N ₂ O: 0-320 ppm H ₂ O: 0-32000 ppm CO ₂ : 0-32000 ppm
Vaisala	Sensor	WR	GMP252 Carbon Dioxide Probe	CO ₂ : 0-10000 ppm (0-20 % also available) CO ₂ : 0-2000 or 0-5000 ppm
Axetris	Sensor	WR	LGD Compact A (CH ₄)	CH ₄ : 0-200 ppm
Dräger	Sensor	WR	Polytron 8100 EC (NH ₃)	NH ₃ : 0-100 ppm
Healthy Photon	Instrument	TNO	Open path QCLAS HT8700E (Mobile HT TNO)	NH ₃ : 0-1260 ppb (indoor) NH ₃ : 0-200; 0-750 ppb (outdoor)
Healthy Photon	Instrument	TNO	Open path QCLAS HT8700E (Flux HT TNO)	NH ₃ : 0-200 ppb
Healthy Photon	Instrument	TNO	Open path QCLAS HT8700E (Flux HT UKCEH)	NH ₃ : 0-100 ppb
Aerodyne	Instrument	TNO	Closed path QC-TILDAS (UKCEH)	NH ₃ : 0-150 ppb
Aerodyne	Instrument	TNO	Closed path QC-TILDAS (vTI)	NH ₃ : 0-150 ppb
Gasera	Analyser	PTB	Photoacoustic spectrometer prototype	NH ₃ : 0-100 ppm CH ₄ : 0-100 ppm N ₂ O: 0-100 ppm H ₂ O: 0-30000 ppm

⁸ <https://aerodyne.com/wp-content/uploads/NH3.pdf>

2.2 Reference materials

Table 2 summarizes the range of measured amount fractions of the different analytes in a wide range of animal housing types, including dairy cattle, pig and poultry farms, with or without outdoor exercise areas, with naturally or mechanically ventilated housing, as reported by project partners at the beginning of the quantiAGREMI project.

Based on these data, the following reference gas mixtures were recommended for calibration and validation experiments in the project, to cover the necessary concentration ranges: 10 % CO₂, 500 ppm and 10 % CH₄, and 25 ppm N₂O, 100 ppb NH₃ in synthetic air matrix (20 % O₂, 80 % N₂). These gas mixtures can be provided by National Metrology Institutes with a relative expanded uncertainty of 1 %.

IMT-Nord-Europe used a primary reference gas mixture of 10 ppm NH₃ (certified value: 9.47 ppm NH₃) in N₂ provided by VSL for testing the AMON NH₃ sensor. This reference gas mixture is then diluted with clean air (dry or humidified) to achieve ammonia concentration between 0 and 200 ppb.

CMI provided a standard of 506.7 ppm CH₄ in air and TUBITAK of 10 % CO₂ in air to WR. Other traceable gas cylinders in N₂ were used where appropriate (mainly from Scott specialty gases, Breda NL). Cylinders were available at minimum ~10 and ~100 ppm for NH₃, ~100 and ~450 ppm for CH₄ and ~2.000 and ~4.500 ppm for CO₂. Cylinders were intercompared and used in conjunction during the sensor testing.

TNO used a primary reference gas mixture of 100 ppm NH₃ (certified value: 102.43 ppm) together with a dynamic dilution system, both provided by VSL. Using this system, NH₃ reference gas mixtures in the ppb range can be generated in dry or wet air with a relative expanded uncertainty (k=2) around 2.7%.

PTB's reference CRDS spectrometer for NH₃ [1] has been used in the 0-10 ppm range to calibrate the NH₃ channel of the photoacoustic spectrometer prototype developed by Gasera, while PTB's reference TDLAS spectrometer for H₂O [2] was used in the 0-2 % (absolute humidity) range to calibrate the H₂O channel of the Gasera spectrometer. Furthermore, two gas mixtures prepared by CMI, 500 ppm CH₄ in synthetic air, and 25 ppm N₂O in synthetic air were used to calibrate the CH₄ and N₂O channel of the spectrometer.

Table 2.: Measured amount fractions of the different analytes in practical applications

Analyte	lowest measured concentrations / ppm	highest
NH ₃	0.01	72.7
CH ₄	1.8	504.9
CO ₂	415	4890.7
N ₂ O	0	22.8
	relative humidity in % at temperatures -11 to 35 °C	
H ₂ O	19	100

2.3 Testing laboratories

Wageningen Livestock Research as part of Wageningen University & Research, operates a dedicated Air Quality Laboratory (AQL) to carry out the measurements for emission related projects. Calibration facilities cover all relevant gases and flow rates over a wide range and are used to characterize equipment, deliver (initial) calibration lines and provide ongoing quality control e.g. by checks before/after maintenance. In field deployment typically regular reference measurements, wet chemistry for NH₃ and air sampling followed by GC analysis for GHGs are performed. This yields field calibration lines to correct for conditions actually encountered in specific situations, due to interferences and circumstances.

For laboratory tests/calibrations of gaseous components the AQL operates a dynamic dilution system consisting of a dedicated mass flow controller per gas (Bronkhorst EL-FLOW Prestige), a gas mixing chamber

and air humidifying system (Bronkhorst CORI-FLOW plus Controlled Evaporation Mixer unit) connected through stainless steel and/or PTFE tubing. A photo of the set-up is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Dynamic gas dilution system used by WR. Left hand side MFCs per gas and mixing chamber, right hand side humidifying system (CORI-FLOW partly visible).

The AMON ammonia gas sensors were tested and calibrated on an analytical bench at IMT-Nord-Europe. A primary NH_3 gas mixture of 10 ppm NH_3 in nitrogen provided by VSL is diluted with clean air by using three Bronkhorst EL FLOW mass flow controllers (MFC). Two MFCs of 10 L/min are used to control dry and wet clean air to manage the system's relative humidity. The combination of two MFCs in dry air and humid air allows to control the final relative humidity obtained in the mixing chamber. The conducted experiments target relative humidity of 20 %, 30 % and 40 %. A third MFC of 0.5 L/min is used to control the NH_3 concentration, targeting a range of ammonia concentration between 0 and 200 ppb. The final gas mixture is sent to a 5 L glass mixing chamber with a flow rate of 10 L/min to interact with the AMON sensor. Additionally, the final gas mixture is analyzed by a Picarro G2103 (NH_3) instrument. Figure 2 depicts the schematics of the set-up used at IMT-Nord-Europe.

Figure 2: Test bench at IMT-Nord-Europe for AMON sensors testing and calibration.

PTB is the national metrology institute in Germany. Its laser spectroscopic laboratories in the working group 3.42. “Spectroscopic gas analysis and reference data” in Braunschweig, Germany, offer the possibility of calibrating instruments against optical gas standards, i.e. reference spectrometers, which are suitable for absolute, traceable amount fraction measurements. This method is particularly advantageous in the case of reactive or adsorptive analytes, where the preparation and application of static gas mixtures is challenging. PTB holds a calibration and measurement capability (CMC) for measuring hydrogen chloride amount fractions in biomethane using tunable diode absorption spectroscopy (TDLAS) [3]. In the presented experiments two further reference spectrometers were used: a TDLAS spectrometer for measuring water vapor [2] and a cavity ring-down spectrometer (CRDS) for measuring ammonia amount fractions [1]. Test gas mixtures were prepared by dynamic dilution with purified ambient air, using gas cylinders with higher amount fractions of the analytes and calibrated mass flow controllers. Humidity was added to the gas mixture by a two-pressure humidity generator. The reference amount fraction values of NH_3 and H_2O were provided by the reference spectrometers. Reference amount fractions of N_2O and CH_4 were calculated from the amount fractions given on certified primary gas mixtures (provided by CMI) and the dilution ratios. A photo of the laboratory set-up with instruments under test, as well as reference spectrometers is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: PTB's laboratory set-up with reference spectrometers and instruments under test

Three HT8700E open path spectrometers and two Aerodyne-TILDAS spectrometers were tested by TNO in Petten, the Netherlands. Two HT8700E spectrometers are owned by TNO, one being used for mobile measurements on a truck (referred to as “mobile HT”), the other for NH_3 flux measurements at a field site (referred to as “flux HT”). The third spectrometer is owned by UKCEH and is being used for flux measurements in the field (“flux HT CEH”). The two Aerodyne-TILDAS spectrometers are owned by vTI and UKCEH and were used in the quantiAGREMI project in various field measurement campaigns [4]. Calibrations were performed in the laboratory, next to a Dutch dairy farm, and outdoors on TNO's premises.

During testing the HT8700E devices the biggest challenge is that it is an open-path spectrometer. For calibration a glass cell with 3.7 L volume was mounted air-tight between the body of the HT8700E and the mirror holder, with the laser path enclosed. The glass cell had a gas inlet port close to the body of the device and a gas outlet port close to the mirror, and continuous flow of the gaseous standards provided by VSL's reference gas mixture system was maintained. The open path instrument was thereby converted to a closed path device, which made calibrations with gas mixtures possible.

The Areodyne-TILDAS instruments require a high flow rate, approximately a factor of 2 higher than what the reference gas mixture can provide. For calibration, the reference gas from the generator was diluted by clean air with 1:1 dilution ratio, to achieve the necessary flow rate.

Figure 4: a) VSL's reference gas generator system set-up at the TNO Petten laser lab for indoor calibration of the TNO mobile HT and flux HT devices, b) The reference gas generator system outside the TNO Petten lab to calibrate TNO mobile HT, c) Field calibration of the UKCEH flux HT device with the glass cell enclosing the laser path.

3 Results

3.1 Laboratory tests of Senseair and Vaisala sensors at WR

WR tested the Senseair K96 devices 1138E (CH₄/CO₂/H₂O) and 115B5 (N₂O/CO₂/H₂O), which are prototypes of newly developed sensors. Furthermore, WR tested different commercial sensors, which were used in field campaigns of the project: three Vaisala GMP252 CO₂ sensors, two Axetris LGD Compact-A CH₄ sensors and two Dräger Polytron 8100 EC NH₃ sensors.

For optimized use of the Vaisala GMP252 CO₂ sensors on the analog data acquisition system used by WR, their measurement range has been modified to either 0-2000 ppm or 0-5000 ppm. The former is for air going in the barns or naturally ventilated situations, and the second for mechanical ventilation where concentrations are typically higher. Three sensors were tested, which are referred to by their WR inventory number: Vaisala 247 (original serial nr. U3050880) being low and 126 (V1941221) and 198 (V1941318) being high range.

During the tests response time, detection limit, repeatability, calibration and (moisture) interference were determined. The first three repetitions of zero and span (chosen were 506.7 ppm CH₄ and 1781 ppm CO₂) values are applied, with rise and fall times to reach 90% giving the response time (t_{90}). Thereafter a calibration line is derived by stepwise increasing the concentration and then decreasing again to also catch hysteresis if this might occur. Sensor responses are calculated as the average over the last minute from each step. The calibration line is then found by linear regression and its uncertainty or lack-of-fit ($u(lof)$) by:

$$u(lof) = \frac{\rho_{max}}{\sqrt{3}} \quad (1)$$

With ρ_{max} the largest deviation between supplied and measured concentration. Repeatability is derived from its standard deviation s_r at span:

$$s_r = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(C_i - C_m)^2}{N-1}} \quad (2)$$

With C_i being the sensor response for time intervals of $4 \times t_{90}$ at minimum, C_m the average sensor response and N the number of measurements. Repeatability is then found as $t\sqrt{2}s_r$ (with t the Student t-value for the

degrees of freedom, two for three repetitions). Detection limit is calculated in a similar way but with standard deviation at zero and amounts to $3s_r$.

Figure 5 and Table 3 show the calibration results and metrics for the Senseair sensors.

Figure 5: Calibration results Senseair sensors, top left CH₄ and bottom left N₂O with right panels associated CO₂ measurements.

Table 3: Metrics for the Senseair sensors (note that for N₂O only a limited calibration was conducted, as concentrations to be expected in practice would be in the lowest part of the measurement range).

	Calibration line	R ²	u(lof) / ppm	t ₉₀ / s	s _r / ppm	Detection limit / ppm
1138E CH ₄	$y = 0.851 x - 199.9$	1.0000	186.66	77	0.190	0.927
1138E CO ₂	$y = 0.965 x - 8.55$	1.0000	91.44	103	0.526	0.970
115B5 N ₂ O	$y = 1.041 x + 7.69$	0.9998	-4.26	-	-	-
115B5 CO ₂	$y = 1.006 x + 23.4$	1.0000	-12.45	-	-	-

Results show good linearity as shown by the high R²-scores, and no hysteresis was observed. However, calibration is necessary given the slopes and intercepts found, also translating in sizeable calibration uncertainties. Senseair informed that they apply their standard calibration model optimized for typical Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning (HVAC) industrial applications, where an accuracy of +/- (30 ppm + 3 % of reading) is often required. As a criterium an expanded uncertainty ($u(lof)$ multiplied by coverage factor 2) not exceeding 8% of the span value set by NVN-CEN/TS 17660:1 for class 1 sensor systems in ambient could be used. In that case the Senseair sensors would currently be applicable where higher CO₂ concentrations are expected (i.e. mechanically ventilated barns), indicating that raw sensor output would need improvement. Response time would suffice for most monitoring tasks, as usually longer integration times like hourly values are considered. For the repeatability WR has a criterium of 5 % of the 95 %-percentile under the conditions where sensor is to be operated. As an example: if in a pig barn 95 % of measured CO₂ concentrations were

3000 ppm or below, repeatability should not exceed $3000 \times 0.05 = 150$ ppm. Only under low concentrations of CH₄ (for instance poultry) this would not be met with Senseair devices tested. Detection limits (criteria 5 ppm CH₄ or CO₂) are also within range.

During testing N₂O and H₂O were found to be cross-sensitive to CO₂ (see Figure 6a). Additionally, moisture interference for each component (except N₂O) was investigated. This was done at two to four concentrations with dry and 20-30, 40-50, 70-80 and 90-95% RH gas. Moisture interference is seen in the raw sensor output for CH₄ (also N₂O at the zero level) but not for CO₂, see Figure 6 and 7. These interferences are known by Senseair and mainly explained by spectral absorption overlaps in the measured wavelength regions. The multi-gas capability of the K96 sensor is intended to correct for these interferences, but as of today there is no automatic compensation of the cross-sensitivities implemented in the K96 firmware. Methods were tested by Senseair during the project as reported in deliverable 4 [4].

Figure 6: Examples of observed cross-sensitivity a) N₂O response during calibration of CO₂ and b) moisture interference on CH₄. Note that following this it was also tested for CO₂, showing no significant interference for humidity.

Figure 7: Moisture interference on Senseair sensors for a) on CH₄ measurements with the 1138E sensor, and on CO₂ measurements with b) the 1138E sensor and c) with the 115B5 sensor.

In numerical terms moisture interference at high CH₄ concentration (506.7 ppm) resulted in an increase in the measured CH₄ concentration by 35 % going from dry gas to RH between 90-95%. Since the difference gets larger with increasing RH and enhances at low CH₄ concentration (50.5 ppm), this might indicate a deviation in the slope of the H₂O measurement of the sensor. For CO₂ measurements, moisture interference always stayed below 1 %.

Figure 8 and Table 4 show the calibration results and metrics for the Vaisala sensors. Results for the Axetris (CH₄) and Dräger (NH₃) sensors have been added to Table 4 for completeness.

Figure 8: Calibration results Vaisala sensors, note that top row are sensors with 0-5000 ppm range and bottom one 0-2000 ppm (graph scaled equally for comparison).

Table 4: Metrics for the Vaisala, Axetris and Dräger sensors.

Sensor		Calibration line	R ²	u(lof) / ppm	t ₉₀ / s	S _r / ppm	Detection limit / ppm
Vaisala-126	CO ₂	y = 1.005 x – 4,27	0.9999	8.89	87	5.084	-
Vaisala-198	CO ₂	y = 0,998 x – 3,22	0.9999	17.42	88	3.947	-
Vaisala-247	CO ₂	y = 0.979 x + 0.83	0.9998	26.27	102	1.549	0.281
Axetris-22	CH ₄	y = 0.996 x + 0.42	1.0000	0.298	60*	0.058	0.014
Axetris-23	CH ₄	y = 0.999 x + 0.09	1.0000	0.194	60*	0.065	0.014
Dräger-20	NH ₃	y = 0.853 x - 0.02	0.9999	0.036	120*	0.100	0.357
Dräger-22	NH ₃	y = 0.875 x	0.9999	0.043	120*	0.101	0.217

* During regular laboratory calibrations, response time is being rounded to the next minute.

The Vaisala sensors show good linearity as shown by the high R²-scores, and no hysteresis was observed. Slopes and intercepts are nearing 1 and 0 respectively. Calibration uncertainty suffices for most applications but is close to the acceptable level for the sensor used for the Vaisala-247 sensor (which was incidentally the least performing of the three, but used for the ingoing air, i.e. highest requirements). Response time is well within needs for most monitoring tasks, where longer integration times, e.g. hourly values are usual. Although repeatability values are higher than with the Senseair devices, these still fulfil the criterium of 5% at the 95%-percentile of the application, also for ingoing air where the range will be the smallest. Detection limit could not be determined properly in the high range Vaisala sensors, because data at low concentration were not reported with sufficient resolution. This is a limitation of the data acquisition, which will be reconsidered.

3.2 Laboratory tests of the AMON ammonia sensor performed at IMT Nord-Europe

The AMON sensors are designed to measure low NH₃ concentrations in outside air, which were developed and tested at IMT Nord-Europe. Laboratory tests on prototypes of the sensor were conducted by increasing ammonia concentration by 50 ppb every 30 minutes in the gas mixing chamber described earlier, starting at 0 ppb and reaching 200 ppb (Figure 9a). These ammonia cycles were repeated at three different relative humidity levels: 20 %, 30 % and 40 % RH, to determine the impact of humidity on the sensors' sensitivity.

Figure 9: a) exposure protocol of ammonia in the mixing gas chamber at three different relative humidity (blue) levels (20 – 30 – 40 % RH). Ammonia concentration (green) increased by 50 ppb every 30 min, from 0 to 200 ppb and was measured by a Picarro analyser. 4 hours of cleaning with dry clean air were conducted between each cycle, b) Example of an AMON sensor (violet) to an increasing amount of NH₃, compared to the analyser’s response (green). c) Sensor versus analyser response to increasing NH₃ concentration at three different relative humidity levels. The equation of the linear regression corresponds to the sensitivity of the sensor in each case.

Table 5: Mean values of sensor’s sensitivity (a) for the example above (Figure 9c) at three different relative humidity (RH) and the R² of the linear regression associated

RH	a	b	R ²
30%	626.64	-668.35	0.96
20%	749.05	-991.1	0.96
40%	643.57	-736.25	0.96

The AMON sensors’ response to ammonia was then compared to the response of the Picarro analyzer in order to determine the sensitivity of the sensor (Figure 9b and c). The results showed that the AMON sensor can effectively detect ammonia concentration in the ppb range and that relative humidity has an important impact on the sensor’s sensitivity, as also demonstrated by Da Silva et al. 2023 [5]. An algorithm developed at IMT-Nord-Europe allows to accelerate the response of the sensors in post-processing by taking into account the derivative and acceleration of the signal.

On figure 9b and 10a, NH₃ injection time might seem too short to allow the signal to stabilize. However, by using the acceleration algorithm which allows to artificially reach stabilization, we have been able to determine that the sensors sensitivity (linear regression) is similar with and without stabilization for this exposition time to NH₃. That is why, in addition to saving us experimental time, we have chosen to maintain an injection time of 30 minutes.

Another part of the laboratory tests focused on the impact of the flow channel configuration on sensor capacity. Impact of three parameters were tested: fan speed, presence or absence of an obstacle called a vortex generator (VG) and the channel height. The tests were conducted by increasing ammonia concentration by 25 ppb every 30 min, starting at 0 ppb and reaching 100 ppb (Figure 10). All measurements were performed under stable relative humidity of 40 %. Due to patent concerns, the parameters will be referred as speed V 1-2, channel 1-2 and height 1-2 (Figure 10), specific values cannot be given here.

Figure 10: a) Comparison between ammonia concentration measured by our sensor (blue) and the analyzer (green) in ppm. b) Schematic of the flow channel used for these experiments. c) Results of the experiments where all configurations were tested (except height 2 and channel 2 which are incompatible) and expressed as relative voltage slope also called sensor sensitivity.

Results of these tests showed that each parameter seemed to have an impact on the sensor capacity (Figure 10). The configurations 3 and 5 offer the best sensitivity (relative voltage slope). However, having the best sensitivity is not our main goal. For outdoor tests, stability and reproducibility are also requested. That's why, we suggest that the configuration 1, with the speed V 1, channel 1 and height 1 is the most suitable for field studies (Figure 10).

3.3 Testing Gasera’s photoacoustic spectrometer prototype at PTB

Gasera Ltd. has investigated the feasibility of measuring NH₃, N₂O, CH₄ and H₂O amount fractions simultaneously, using a single quantum cascade laser and highly sensitive photoacoustic spectroscopy with an optical microphone. Results obtained during calibration of the prototype of such an instrument at PTB are presented in this section.

At PTB, NH₃ amount fractions of 26-71 ppb and 1.8-10 ppm have been generated in purified ambient air containing approx. 1.5 % H₂O (corresponding to approx. 75 % RH). Figure 11a shows an example of the time series of the measured amount fractions by the PTB and Gasera spectrometers at a low amount fraction, at 57 nmol/mol, while figure 11b shows measurement results up to 10 ppm.

Figure 12 shows the obtained calibration curve. The Gasera spectrometer shows very good linearity over the whole range with a negligible offset. A slope of 1.5 indicates the necessity of thorough calibration.

Figure 11: Time series of the measured NH₃ and H₂O amount fractions at 1.5 % H₂O amount fraction and a) at 57 ppb NH₃ amount fraction and b) three amount fraction steps from 1.8 to 10 ppm NH₃ amount fraction.

Figure 12: Calibration curve for NH₃ amount fractions between 20 ppb and 10 ppm, in zero air with 1.5 % absolute humidity.

As a next step the H₂O concentration was varied between 0.5 and 2 % at a constant NH₃ amount fraction of 3.5 ppm. Figure 13 shows the time series of the measured NH₃ and H₂O amount fractions. The calibration curve derived from these measurements is depicted in Figure 14 and shows very good linearity of the Gasera

spectrometer, and a small offset. As in the case of NH₃, long-term stability of the calibration parameters must be further investigated.

Figure 13: Time series of the measured NH₃ and H₂O concentrations at 3.5 ppm NH₃ concentration and absolute humidity varied in 4 steps from 0.5 to 2 %.

Figure 14: Calibration curve for H₂O concentrations 0.5 - 2 %, in zero air containing 3.5 ppm NH₃.

Calibration of the CH₄ and N₂O channels has been performed in the 0-50 and 0-2 μmol/mol range, respectively. A slope of 0.89 and 1.02 has been measured, which indicates good accuracy of the spectrometer for these analytes.

Cross-sensitivities were observed in many cases, however, the most prominent was the effect of varying H₂O amount fraction on the measured NH₃ amount fractions. Figure 15 shows the NH₃ concentrations measured by the Gasera spectrometer as a function of H₂O concentrations measured by PTB's reference spectrometer. As can be seen in the Figure, approx. 10 % difference has been observed between the NH₃ concentration readings at 0.5 and 2 % H₂O concentration. Further measurements need to be performed to explore dependence of this cross-sensitivity on the NH₃ concentration level, and development of a correction algorithm will be necessary to obtain accurate NH₃ concentration results.

Figure 15: NH_3 amount fractions measured by the Gasera spectrometer, as a function of H_2O amount fractions measured by PTB's reference spectrometer. During these measurements the NH_3 amount fraction was kept constant at 3.5 mmol/mol and purified air containing ~ 2 mmol/mol CH_4 and ~ 200 nmol/mol N_2O was used as matrix gas.

Furthermore, a cross-sensitivity between CH_4 and NH_3 has been observed, and an empirical correction based on laboratory measurements was used in the field measurements to avoid negative CH_4 readings at high NH_3 amount fractions.

3.4 Laboratory and field tests of high-end NH_3 instruments performed at TNO

TNO presented detailed calibration methods and results during the project, which are documented in a publicly available TNO report [6]. In this document, we show and discuss the most important results of this work. Table 6 summarizes the test parameters and conditions of the different calibration runs performed on high-end NH_3 monitoring instruments. The range of calibration parameters was selected based on the applications of the different instruments. The mobile HT is typically used for mobile measurements in or near livestock barns, where NH_3 concentrations can exceed 1 ppm. Therefore, a higher calibration range was applied to this system. In contrast, the flux HT systems, both from TNO and UKCEH, as well as the TILDAS instruments were primarily used at greater distances from emission sources, for example in nature reserves, where the instrument captures lower NH_3 concentrations. These analyzers are therefore calibrated in a lower concentration range.

Table 6: Test parameters and conditions of the calibration runs for the HT and TILDAS instruments.

NH_3 instrument	Owner	Calibration location	Calibration range (ppb)	RH (%)	Temperature ($^{\circ}C$)
Mobile HT	TNO	TNO lab, indoor	0 – 1260	5 – 55	21 – 25*
		TNO lab, outdoor	0 – 750	0 – 35	8 – 16*
Flux HT	UKCEH	Dairy farm, field	0 – 100	0 – 35	8 – 19*
Flux HT	TNO	TNO lab, indoor	0 – 200	0 – 60	20 – 23*
TILDAS	UKCEH	Dairy farm, field	0 – 150	0	23**
TILDAS	vTI	Dairy farm, field	0 – 150	0	25**

*Ambient temperature, i.e. temperature of the open cell

**internally controlled instrument temperature, the spectrometer is placed in a temperature-controlled box.

3.4.1. Calibration of the TNO mobile HT instrument

During the indoor tests before application in the field a set of different concentration values was tested in steps of 3 hours, as depicted in Figure 16a. For the highest RH-settings (50-55 %) NH_3 concentrations of 0, 28.5, 72, 142, 285, 710, and 1262 ppb were applied using both upward and downward ramps. For the other humidity settings subsets of these were used. The temperature in the lab remained stable between 21-25 $^{\circ}C$ and a

constant flow rate of 3.5 L min^{-1} was maintained throughout the calibration. During the outdoor tests on TNO's premises after a mobile field measurement campaign (

Figure 166b), concentration levels of 0, 20, 50, 100, 200, 500, and 750 ppb were supplied to the HT on top of the truck trailer under dry ($\text{RH} < 5\%$) and semi-dry ($\text{RH} \approx 33\%$) conditions.

a)

b)

c)

Figure 16: Time series of concentrations and relative humidity levels during the calibration runs of the mobile HT system and regression analysis. a) indoor calibration performed inside the TNO laboratory; b) outdoor calibration after mobile drive, performed at TNO. c) Regressions for outdoor calibration: without temperature correction at different RH in the left; with temperature correction at dry condition in the right.

According to Table 7, regression analyses confirm a linear response of the mobile HT both before and after the field measurements, with R^2 values close to 1. Good linearity is observed independent of the indoor or outdoor location and of the relative humidity, although smaller changes in the offset and slope can be observed. The observed slopes are significantly deviating from 1. However, this was expected, since the instrument was

previously sent back to the manufacturer for quick repair and thereafter received without proper pre-calibration by the manufacturer. Agreement between the results of the different calibrations is acceptable.

Table 7: Results of the regression analysis of the data in Figure 16. For the indoor test humidity conditions were too unstable to compare. For the outdoor tests a comparison of dry and semi-dry conditions could be made.

	Offset	Std. error offset	Slope	Std error slope	R ²
Indoor before field test, all data (RH≈10-55%)	8.55	0.59	0.445	0.001	0.998
<i>Indoor VSL < 200 ppb (RH 10-55%)</i>	<i>0.16</i>	<i>0.12</i>	<i>0.505</i>	<i>0.002</i>	<i>0.999</i>
Outdoor after field test, all data	-2.12	0.67	0.483	0.002	0.997
<i>Outdoor after field test, dry (RH ≈ 0%)</i>	<i>-2.35</i>	<i>0.64</i>	<i>0.492</i>	<i>0.002</i>	<i>0.998</i>
<i>Outdoor after field test, semi-dry (RH ≈ 33%)</i>	<i>-1.93</i>	<i>1.11</i>	<i>0.474</i>	<i>0.003</i>	<i>0.996</i>
<i>Outdoor after field test, dry, VSL < 200 ppb</i>	<i>-3.23</i>	<i>0.55</i>	<i>0.499</i>	<i>0.004</i>	<i>0.997</i>
VSL < 800 ppb, no temperature correction	-2.35	0.64	0.492	0.002	0.998
VSL < 800 ppb, temperature correction	0.18	0.00	0.507	0.000	1.000
VSL < 200 ppb, no temperature correction	-3.92	0.37	0.502	0.003	0.996
VSL < 200 ppb, temperature correction	0.16	0.00	0.507	0.004	1.000

The regression results in Table 7 suggest a negative effect of increasing relative humidity on the slope of the calibration line, as well as stabilization issues, which might cause hysteresis above 200 ppb. The details of these effects are discussed in detail in Ref. [6].

Outdoor calibration of the mobile HT was followed by an additional 24 hours temperature dependence check at a fixed concentration level of 50 ppb and dry conditions (RH < 5 %). A drift in the measured concentration values was observed, strongly correlated to the measured temperature (Figure 17a). To compensate for this, TNO implemented a combined correction approach for the data of the outdoor calibration: First, a linear regression was applied using the reference NH₃ measurements provided by VSL's reference gas generator (referred to as VSL in the figures). Second, a second-order polynomial correction was introduced based on the HT's inner water circular temperature sensor. This correction method significantly improved the accuracy of the NH₃ measurements under varying temperature conditions.

During the mobile HT outdoor calibration period, the HT ambient temperature, internal temperature, and water circular temperature were recorded. It was observed that the offset of the calibration are most affected by the HT water circular temperature, with only minor impact on the slope. After applying the temperature correction shown in Figure 17b the new calibrated line's slopes and offsets are closer to the indoor calibration equation (see Figure 16b and Table 7).

Figure 17: Results of the temperature check in dry conditions after the outdoor calibration run. During this check, a) Difference between HT and VSL measured NH₃ concentrations (HT - VSL) plotted against various temperature parameters: internal HT temperature, external HT temperature, and water cooling pump temperature. b) Correlation analysis of (HT calib¹ - VSL) vs. the three temperature variables. Pearson correlation coefficients (R²) are calculated to assess the goodness of fit. Note that HT calib¹ is obtained by applying the low-concentration range (VSL<200ppb) lab calibration equation in Figure 16a zoom in plot.

3.4.2. Calibration of the flux HT instruments from TNO and UKCEH

During calibration of the TNO flux HT device each calibration point was maintained for 1.5 hours, with a constant flow rate of 3 L min⁻¹. Also the flux HT system of TNO demonstrates a very linear response at all humidity levels (Figure 18). The R² of the fit on all data is 1.0, which is also the case for all humidity levels separately. However, there is a large offset in the data of about 31 ppb. Similarly to the mobile HT device, a slight decrease in slope is observed, when RH increases (see Table 8).

Figure 18: Time series of concentrations and relative humidity levels during the indoor calibration runs of the TNO flux HT system and regression analysis on all cleaned data.

The UKCEH-flux HT calibration was performed outside the dairy farm, using concentrations of 100, 50, 25, 10, 5 and 0 ppb under dry and 20–30 % RH conditions. Each step lasted 1 hour (first series) or 1.5 hours (second series). The measurements and regression results of this system are shown in Figure 19. Compared to the other two tested HT systems, the UKCEH flux HT exhibited greater measurement instability, likely due to larger short-term variations in ambient temperature and RH during the test period. Investigation of temperature effects and thereafter applying temperature correction, like in case of the TNO mobile HT instrument, was not possible for this instrument due to shortness of time. It should also be noted that under dry conditions both the TNO mobile HT and UKCEH-flux HT showed similar calibration slopes, possibly resulting from an improper pre-calibration procedure at the manufacturer. Based on these data, it is recommended to use at least 1.5 hour per calibration step and perform calibration in the field at low concentrations and dry condition only (which is also the most relevant range).

Figure 19: Time series of concentrations and relative humidity levels during the indoor calibration runs of the TNO flux HT and outdoor calibration runs of the UKCEH flux HT and their regression analysis.

Table 8: Results of the regression analysis of the data in Figure 18 and 19.

	Offset	Std. error offset	Slope	Std error slope	R ²
TNO flux HT all data	31.34	0.19	0.934	0.002	0.999
TNO flux HT RH ≈ 0%	29.55	0.19	0.980	0.002	1.000
TNO flux HT RH ≈ 30-40%	31.53	0.19	0.925	0.002	1.000
TNO flux HT RH ≈ 50-60%	31.90	0.20	0.919	0.002	0.999
TNO flux HT VSL < 200 ppb (mixed RH)	31.05	0.22	0.940	0.003	0.999
UKCEH flux HT all stable data	3.72	0.53	0.335	0.009	0.966
UKCEH flux HT RH ≈ 0%, T = 22°C	3.27	0.12	0.454	0.004	0.999
UKCEH flux HT RH ≈ 20-30%, T = 18-22°C	2.83	0.46	0.337	0.007	0.986

3.4.3. Field calibration of the TILDAS instruments of UKCEH and vTI

Field calibration of the UKCEH TILDAS system was conducted near a dairy farm. During the calibration wind came from the north (with clean background) at 6–8 m/s and ambient NH₃ levels were around 2-3 ppb. To meet the TILDAS’s 13 L/min flow requirement, 6.5 L/min of calibrated VSL gas was mixed with 6.5 L/min of ambient air. The results are shown in Figure 20a. The TILDAS system from vTI was calibrated directly after the TILDAS of UKCEH using the same VSL concentration range and near-zero humidity, under the same ambient conditions. 5.8 L/min flow from the reference gas generator was mixed with 5.8 L/min ambient air to meet the instrument’s flow requirement of 11.6 L/min. Ambient NH₃ levels were monitored using the high-accuracy mini-DOAS open-path instrument, and its readings were used to calculate the reference NH₃ concentration reaching the TILDAS instruments. The results of the calibrations are given in Figure 19. In the regression analysis, the highest concentration value and the zero point were excluded because neither stabilized during the measurement period. Although both TILDAS systems stabilize quickly, i.e. within 15 minutes and respond linearly, it seems that the systems structurally underestimate the concentration by about 27-30%. It is however important to note that the TILDAS instruments in this study were optimised for flux measurements (10 Hz) and had no background subtraction applied, which is likely to have resulted in a difference the reported accuracy and precision, than in previous studies, where TILDAS instruments optimised for concentration measurements (1 Hz) were used [7].

Figure 19: Calibration and linear regression results for the two TILDAS systems of (a) UKCEH and (b) vTI.

Table 10: Results of the regression analysis of the data in Figure 19.

	Offset	Std. error offset	Slope	Std error slope	R ²
TILDAS UKCEH stable data , dry	3.85	0.03	0.703	0.001	1.000
TILDAS vTI stable data, dry	4.64	0.10	0.722	0.002	1.000

4 Conclusions

In this report we presented results of laboratory characterization of different sensors and instruments for monitoring NH₃, CH₄, N₂O and CO₂ emissions from agricultural sources. Tests were conducted in a wide variety of concentration ranges, depending on the analyte and the application area (indoor monitoring in barns, and measurements outside at different distances from agricultural sources). Experimental conditions were also different, including some calibrations being carried out under field conditions. We faced various challenges during this work, e.g. finding a suitable chamber for enclosing in-situ sensors, designing a gas cell around an open-path spectrometer, supplying sufficient reference gas flow for instruments with very high flow requirements, and preparing reference gas mixtures containing more than one analyte to test cross-sensitivities.

The investigated sensors and instruments showed overall good performance, linearity was found to be excellent in all cases. However, some results show that regular calibration is extremely important, and larger deviation from the expected values (both slope of the calibration line and zero offset) can even occur in case of sophisticated, high-end instrumentation. Low-cost sensors were generally found to be suitable for indoor monitoring in barns due to their higher detection limit, with some novel sensors being suitable for monitoring lower outdoor concentrations as well. More complex analyzers offering higher sensitivity are usually suitable for monitoring outdoor air, further away from sources, and even background concentrations. Cross-sensitivities were observed in several cases, and especially in case of newly developed sensors and analyzers. Further work will be necessary to accurately quantify these cross-sensitivities and develop correction algorithms.

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